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ASSESSMENT OF THE ACCEPTANCE OF MICROALGAE AS SUPPLEMENT OF FOOD IN THE BOP SECTOR OF PUNE

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ABSTRACT

Bottom of the wealth pyramid is about 80 percent of India's population who suffer from extreme poverty and malnutrition . Spirulina and Chlorella are the most widely noted microalgae full of nutrition that can be consumed separately or in combination with food as a cheap food supplement to eradicate poverty and malnutrition among the BOP sector. An assessment to find the acceptability of this microalgae as food supplement is being focused in this research paper . The research study could be applied to generate alternate income opportunity for underprivileged people in future for growing the microalgae in tanks for both personal consumption as well as commercialization.

Keywords : Bottom of the pyramid , Spirulina ,Chorella malnutrition ,poverty eradication, cheaper alternative .

Background :

BOP - The **bottom of the pyramid** , also known as the bottom of the income / wealth pyramid is the biggest , but most impoverished class. In global terms, this is the four billion people who live on less than say Rs. 67,000 per year. The phrase BOP is generally used by business using innovative business models using technology with this particular sector. . This field is also often referred to as the **Base of the Pyramid** or just the **BoP**.

Innovation in the BoP

There is a traditional view that BOP consumers do not want to adopt innovation easily. C. K. Prahalad (2005) is always reinforce his view that the BOP market always welcomes innovation.. For example , BOP people are using PC kiosks, Mobile phone, Mobile banking etc. Relative advantage and Complexity criteri of an innovation suggested by Everett Rogers (2004) greatly influence the adoption of an innovation in the BOP market (Rahman, Hasan, and Floyd, 2013). Therefore, innovation developed for this market should focus on these two attributes (Relative advantage and Complexity).

Business and community partnerships

Fortune reported on 15th November , 2006 – from 2005 the SC Johnson Company has been working with youth people in the Kibera slum of Nairobi, Kenya. Together SC Johnson and the groups have formed a community-based waste management and cleaning company which provide home-cleaning, insect treatment, and waste disposal services for slum residents . SC Johnson's project was the first establishment of of the "Base of the Pyramid Protocol".

Spirulina was rediscovered during a European scientific mission in Chad (a country in Central Africa), as a traditional food of the locals called Dihé .It was a blue-green, dried cake made of a micro-organism which grew in the natural alkaline lagoons found in this region. It was found that people had been consuming this for centuries not only in Chad but also in Mexico and other areas .Even though people here had extremely poor diet, they did not suffer from malnutrition

Spirulina can become double once in every 2 to 5 days, and can produce over 20 times more protein than soybeans on the same area, and 40 times that of corn and 400 times that of beef .It reduces blood cholesterol .Spirulina helps in controlling diabetes , aids in kidney detoxification, useful in fighting malnutrition .Spirulina is very useful in preventing vitamin a deficiency (helps prevent blindness and eye diseases) .It enhances physical growth as well as cognitive development .It also improves immunity, and therefore helps in fighting and preventing HIV / AIDS and anaemia

Our endeavor to create a low cost food product with optimum nutritions to eradicate malnutrition and hunger in the BOP .It's a form of an edible algae called as "SPIRULINA" often referred to as an blue-green algae .65-71 percent protein and Contains all essential amino acids .It is used as a food supplement to combat malnutrition.1 gram of spirulina is said to be as nutritious as 100grams of spinach or carrots and also cheaper.

Methodology:

Secondary Research

Secondary research comprised collecting data relating to the BOP sector from the varied sources in the public domain.

Primary Research

The research study entailed both qualitative and quantitative research. Survey was done to collect data from around 115 target audience- BOP consumers .On the basis of the literature review and secondary research, a survey questionnaire was designed for the malnourished and underprivileged , to get information about their demographics, awareness and acceptability for microalgae food supplement. The present study used tools like simple percentage .

Limitation of the study

Due to resource constraints and limited access to information, it was difficult to have a large Sample size. Also, BOP respondents were reluctant in sharing information.

Findings & Discussion:

Table 1 : Demographic factors of the respondents

Demographic factor	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Gender		
Male	88	76.52
Female	27	23.47
Total	115	100
Age (in years)		
Below 25	26	22.61
25-35	43	37.39
Above 35	46	40.00
Total	115	100

It was inferred that 88 percent of the respondents were male and the rest female. 40 percent of the respondents belong to the age group above 35 years.

Table 2 : Average Family Income

Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage
150-200	36	31
200-250	79	69
Total	115	100

Majority 69 percent of the respondents earn on an average between Rs. 200-250 per day. Rest 31percent earns around Rs. 150-200 per day.

Table 3 : Number of Family Members

Number	No. of Respondents	Percentage
2	14	12.5
3	14	37.5
4	43	37.5
5	43	12.5
Total	114	100

Majority 75 percent of the respondents has 3-4 family members and the remaining 25 percent of the respondents have either 2 or 5 family members.

Table 4 : Number of Meals

Number	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	14	12.5
2	14	12.5
3	87	75
Total	115	100

Majority 75 percent of the respondents has 3-4 family members and the remaining 25 percent of the respondents have either 2 or 5 family members.

Table 5 : Awareness about food supplement concept

Awareness	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	6	5
No	109	95
Total	115	100

Out of 115 respondents, 5 percent of the respondents were aware of the concept of existence of food supplement.

Table 6 : Acceptance of Food Supplement

Acceptance	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	83	72.17
No	32	27.83
Total	115	100

72.17 percent of the respondents accepted that they will try to supplement their food with the microalgae alternative if found cheap.

Table 7 : Preferred form of Consumption (Picked up more than 1 option)

Reasons	No. of Responses	Percentage of responses
Powder	23	20
Tablet	23	20
Rice	69	60
Roti	92	80
Sabji	115	100
Dal	69	60
Total		

Most of the people ate roti, dal, rice and sabzi but they also mentioned they eat whatever they get to eat. Almost 100 percent of the respondents preferred to consume the food supplement in Sabji form. Next preferred choice were in combination with Rice or Dal.

Significance : This study highlighted that not only for poverty eradication but also for income generation, the microalgae supplement can be used widely by growing them in local tanks at a very low investment.

Conclusions

Bottom of the wealth pyramid is about 80 percent of India's population who suffer from extreme poverty and malnutrition. Spirulina and Chlorella are the most widely noted microalgae full of nutrition that can be consumed separately or in combination with food as a cheap food supplement to eradicate poverty and malnutrition among the BOP sector. An assessment concluded that the BOP sector in Pune is ready to accept the food supplement in combination with their staple food and not as a substitute provided it is cheap.

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